

Transnational Island Museologies

Materials for discussion

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ICOFOM Materials for Discussion

Transnational island museologies

ICOFOM MATERIALS FOR DISCUSSION

This publication brings together papers submitted for the 47th symposium organised by ICOFOM under the theme Transnational Island Museologies, to be held at the University of St Andrews, Scotland, 5-7 June, 2024.

The Materials for Discussion collection brings together, in an inclusive spirit, contributions selected for the symposium in the form of short articles, to prepare the ICOFOM Symposium. This publication has been made available before the symposium, in a very short time frame. In spite of the care given to the publication, some mistakes may remain.

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Part III:
Capitalism and Slavery

***Capitalism and Slavery* round table**

Heather Cateau

University of St. Andrews – Scotland

In 2024 we will commemorate the 80th anniversary of the publication of Eric Williams's seminal work *Capitalism and Slavery*. Although originally published in 1944, the global message of the book still resounds in 2024. Ideas developed in the text are increasingly being revived as we try to understand some of the major challenges of our contemporary world. A related area which is subsumed within *Capitalism and Slavery* is the issue of the perspectives from which history has been written, and by extension, the ways in which the stories of the past have been preserved or presented in books, in our museums and in our memories; as well as the ways in which such histories have shaped our contemporary landscapes. The text and its theses therefore fit neatly with the central themes of this conference. The book provides a road map which can be used to unearth hidden stories and extricate entangled economic, social and cultural spaces. *Capitalism and Slavery* thus has a unique place in our attempt to grapple with the issues connected to emerging transnational island museology.

The themes in *Capitalism and Slavery* have been applied to the relationship between the developed and the developing world; to our understanding of development challenges; and to contemporary movements which focus on economic, social and political equity, such as the Black Lives Matter Movement, the Reparation Movement and current discussions about statues and monuments. Building on this, the round table will share related and relevant ideas as espoused in *Capitalism and Slavery* and apply them in discussions which address issues of representation in history and heritage preservation. The text will therefore be positioned as a basis for discussing some of our contemporary challenges and possible pathways forward.

A round table discussion which engages five contributors will share the perspectives in *Capitalism and Slavery*. The panel will include academics as well as persons connected with history and heritage collection, preservation and dissemination. The insights will therefore come from persons actively grappling with the issues outlined above. Emphasis will be placed on how they have used ideas and themes influenced by *Capitalism and Slavery* in their research and related professional activities to better understand and illuminate history and heritage concerns, as well as to engage the wider community.

Panellists

In keeping with the Shared Island Stories, Scotland the Caribbean: Past, Present, Future Project, which focusses on the historical and contemporary connections between these two geographic spaces, the panellists are from institutions in the Caribbean and Scotland. These two geographic areas share a history that spans at least five centuries, and they are today grappling with embracing and positioning this rich story in our current understanding of ourselves and our societies. The training and occupational specialisations of the panellists facilitate constructive discussion as we

grapple with the multifaceted challenge we face today as we try to create more integrated and equitable societies. This of necessity involves rethinking the past; examining its impact through a 2024 lens; and dealing with the practicalities involved in the dissemination of new ideas. They have collectively all been directly involved in discovery, revisioning, education, dissemination and policy formation. Thus, we will share insights about work done in repositories, research conducted, creative methodologies employed, introduction of new historical narratives, challenges of transmission, continued attempts to educate and implications for our contemporary spaces.

Meet the panel

Heather Cateau, Chair, Senior Research Fellow, University of St. Andrews/University of the West Indies, Trinidad – Shared Island Stories: Scotland and the Caribbean.

Henderson Carter, Head, Department of History, University of the West Indies, Barbados – Street Names and Built Landscape.

Lorna Steele-McGinn, Community Engagement Officer, Highland Archive Centre, Inverness, Scotland – Collection and Preservation.

Stephen Mullen, Lecturer, University of Glasgow, Scotland – Economic Connections.

Diana Paton, William Robertson Professor of History, Head of History, University of Edinburgh, Scotland – Teaching and Learning.

Applying *Capitalism and Slavery* in our contemporary spaces

In his conclusion of *Capitalism and Slavery*, Williams warned that, “The ideas built on ... interests (from previous periods) continue long after the interests have been destroyed and work their old mischief, which is more mischievous because the interests to which they correspond no longer exist” (1944, p. 211). It is therefore fitting that we examine this supposition made in 1944 with respect to the interests that benefitted from sugar and enslavement in the Caribbean and Scotland. Several questions arise: Can these interests continue to work their mischief in 2024? If so, it would be particularly worrying because these are ideas from a period which was characterised by coercive labour systems such as enslavement, racialisation based on skin colour, astronomical profit making and skewed development trajectories. This should not only be worrying but should engender a sense of urgency to grapple with the ramifications. Can we identify the various aberrations in 2024? Do we understand where these ideas have come from? Are we correcting them? Or alternatively, are they still working their old mischief and perhaps have become even more mischievous?

We will start with the academic debates that have come to be identified within *Capitalism and Slavery*. This assessment will begin with a discussion of the major themes in the text and their elaboration in ways that are applicable to our communities in 2024. Williams’s theses on the origins of slavery, the extent of the profitability of the slavery system, and the reasons for emancipation will therefore set the foundation for the rest of the round table. Each panellist will also share individual

perspectives on how the text has shaped her/his research interests and professional activities. These have been elaborated in a series of Think Pieces, included here.

The discussion advances through examining the ways in which *Capitalism and Slavery* can be applied to produce a better understanding of our contemporary spaces. This will include sharing perspectives on implications for history, approaches to tangible and intangible heritage, as well as focus on sites and built landscape in both the Caribbean and Scotland/Britain. This will be further enhanced through sharing collaborations and initiatives in which the panellists have been directly involved to share insights with a wider cross section of the public. We will end by exploring the lessons learnt and the ways in which we can ensure more equity and better representation in how we treat with historical narratives, their preservation and their dissemination.

The think pieces

In “Enabling historiography: the responsibility of the archivist as conduit”, Lorna Steele-McGinn shares insight from her position at the frontlines in the Highland Archive Centre, where they are uncovering a wealth of Caribbean material in their collections and deposits. Many of the collections connect the region to African enslavement. She takes us from discovery to access of archival information in an outline which includes collection, appraisal, cataloguing and dissemination. In so doing she positions archives as both a starting point and an end in the journey to uncover the past and shape the future. She draws us into that journey from the vantage point of archival collections which are really at the base of so much of our understanding about the past. She captures the varied difficulties in establishing what can be described as a full or true story. The challenges start from the initial decisions about what is collected and preserved. The material itself is laden with conscious and unconscious bias, not just of the writers and those handling the material, but even of the eras. Thus, she posits that record keeping itself may be considered as act of writing history. McGuinn clearly establishes a power relationship in the nature of the custodial responsibilities of archives and encourages us to think about issues like, “Who polices the future?” and “Who has the right to tell the story?” Her questioning leads to re-envisioning the role of the archivist from a passive guardian to one which involves not just custodial responsibilities but also a more active role in interpretation and engagement. Thus, McGuinn’s contribution takes us back to *Capitalism and Slavery* and Williams’s warning by showing us exactly how old ideas can continue to shape our present. This think piece makes us cognizant that we must all be on our guard against these old “mischiefs” and demonstrates how archives can play a more dynamic role as we try to shape a more inclusive future with a fuller sense of the past.

Stephen Mullen recounts the life of *Capitalism and Slavery* from 1944 to 2024 in “Historiographical afterlives of *Capitalism and Slavery* and the Williams theses”. He demonstrates that historical analyses, mainstream conclusions and accepted truisms about empire, colonies and African enslavement are not static but change over time. Through these changes the narratives in our societies and indeed of our own perspectives are also transformed. Thus, he contends that the book is representative of shifts not only in historiographical theorising, but also societal understanding. Mullen outlines each of Williams’s theses and examines the body of work spawned by the book. In 2024 research calls into question glorious accounts of the British empire which underplayed the extent of the involvement of Britain’s colonies in its economic development that prevailed to the early twentieth

century. These accounts resisted challenges and were supported by strong defences mounted by historians and publishers. These are indeed examples of the “old mischief” that Williams warned would persist without questioning. Today Williams’s theses have undergone resurgence and much of that questioning has taken place in our contemporary period. There is growing support from studies expanding the depth and range of the colonies’ impact on British commercial and industrial development. Mullen also looks specifically at Scotland, where Williams was ignored until even later in the twentieth century. Through his own path breaking research, as well as new databases and studies, the full contribution of the Caribbean in Scottish commerce, institutions and landscapes are only now being revealed. Mullen ends with a call for continuing the movement from Scottish historiographical orthodoxy to truth-seeking, as we grapple with our shared history of empire and African enslavement.

Diana Paton combines her extensive academic experience with her practical involvement in pathbreaking education projects in “Teaching and learning with and through *Capitalism and Slavery*”. She demonstrates changes in action through timely examples of how the text is being incorporated into the education system in Britain. She elaborates through three of Williams’s theses which continue to engage us: the extent of the impact of African enslavement and the colonies on British economic growth; the reasons for emancipation which has two extremes of humanitarianism and economic self-interest; and the debate as to whether economic factors or racism led to the introduction of the slave system. She cautions against counterfactual claims and conservative think tanks and so echoes Williams’s warning about the mischief that can be done by interests will live on hidden within the framework of our societies. Paton gives practical examples from two innovative projects, Teaching Slavery in Scotland and Living Histories of Sugar, and shares lessons learnt from the approaches used. She advocates the importance of paying attention to the methodologies used to connect today’s learners to the past. She calls for not just intellectual or academic approaches, but what she describes as intuitive approaches. She points to the value of material that can be created by teachers and supports community involvement and engagement. She also cautions about the isolation of factors as we develop revised historical perspectives and reminds us that understanding the past requires a multi-layered approach rather than isolation of any one set of factors. For Paton, teaching and learning must be an ongoing process, and *Capitalism and Slavery* continues to provide inspiration.

In our world today one of the more visible and emotive challenges has become how we treat with areas of our built landscape that are signifiers of a past characterised by enslavement, violence and racism. These imperialist symbols of the power and by extension the subjugation of native and forcefully transported groups have existed silently among us as “great objects”, often without thought to their historical significance or impact on the people in the past and present. The question of who determines the signifiers we choose to place in positions of honour or to use as reference points is one that we are grappling with today. They, too, are representative of the old ideas which Williams warned were reflective of “old interests” which continue their “old mischief”. Henderson Carter develops his insights into this theme through his examination of the current context in Barbados in “Street names and built landscape: Scottish colonial imprint on Barbados”. He draws from his research into the shared history of Barbados and Scotland and shares dimensions of Barbados’ Scottish past that are still present in what he describes as the very imprint of Barbados. This legacy involves not only persons of Scottish ancestry but also surnames, place names and

buildings. Drawing from history, he traces the origins of this imprint and questions the reason for its persistence despite independence and current calls for decolonisation and reparations. For Carter however, it is not a simple matter of removal and change. The process must also be used as a tool for public education and for tourism and heritage development. He describes Barbados as a “country museum of tourism”. Thus, he advocates leveraging these shared stories and connections of the past to bring a better understanding of our landscapes as well as our people.

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Enabling historiography: The responsibility of the archivist as conduit

Lorna Steele-McGinn

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The question of who writes history, and for whom, is one which has arisen for centuries. All historiography carries with it the conscious or unconscious biases, attitudes, and prejudices not only of its author but of its era and context. Raw material in the form of archives is shaped and used to support the theory, belief, or ideological aim of the writer.

But who has provided that raw material? Who has chosen what records should be kept, where they should be stored, how they should be accessed, and by whom? Is the process of recordkeeping an act of writing history?

Archivists, in both professional and non-professional settings, carry that responsibility and, with it, the risk of sustaining or perpetuating inequalities and attitudes through their decision-making at every stage of the process. It is a responsibility which currently weighs heavily on the profession. Archivists have traditionally been employees of the state or other institutions, their wages paid by those whose decision-making in the past has created some of the very inequalities they now strive to address. Archival theory owes much to the work of Sir Charles Hilary Jenkinson, whose *Manual of Archive Administration* has shaped archival principles since its publication in 1922, but who was employed by a government witnessing, and resisting, the end of the British Empire. His vision of archivists as neutral custodians was therefore idealistic, but his dominance in the field has meant that others who have come with different perspectives, such as that of Caribbean theorist Arthur Schomburg, have been overshadowed (Ishmael, 2018).

This paper will seek to examine the ways in which the entire archival process can play a part in both exposing the past and shaping the future, from the collection of records, through appraisal and cataloguing, to enabling access and active dissemination.

Collecting

Archives cannot tell a complete story. Records have been lost over time, some have been actively destroyed to support or obscure a narrative, some never existed because those who could have created them had no opportunity to do so. Archives cannot be neutral because some voices, some experiences, some demographics, will always dominate. Even the most complete collection will not tell a full story.

The question of where archives are and where they should be is part of this narrative. Many collections exist in official institutions because of historic power imbalances – the coloniser's evidence of "ownership". Archives displaced from their country of creation are common, with questions

arising about legitimate ownership and the responsibilities that come with custodianship. Agostinho (2019) illustrates this in relation to archives from the Danish West Indies/US Virgin Islands.

Archives often strive to increase and diversify the voices represented in their collections, but challenges, both practical and emotional, are faced by those handing over archival material to institutions. To what extent does control of the records mean control of the subject of the records (Bastian, 2002, as cited in Agostinho, 2019, p. 149)? How can those relinquishing that control trust the organisations to whom they are giving it? And with archives often resource-thin, how can they offer confidence that collections will be made accessible before years have passed?

The archival accession process has some elements of reassurance. Ownership of archives does not need to be relinquished – collections can be deposited with an archive rather than gifted – ensuring that some control of the content is retained while the physical records are protected. Postcustodial theory suggests that collections do not even need to be deposited in an archive. Owners and creators can maintain the records themselves with the practical and professional assistance of archivists, enabling the documents to be catalogued and made accessible more quickly but potentially risking the loss of some professional standards and protection. Recognising the power, and therefore the responsibility, that comes with officialdom is the first step towards encouraging confidence in the archival process.

Appraisal

Collections that make their way into an archive face an appraisal process, where records deemed to be of long-term value are retained and those classified as having no further value are destroyed or offered back to the depositor. This process, although governed by the collecting policies and remits of individual organisations, is nevertheless unavoidably subjective. The limit to what a document can tell you is only limited by the questions you ask of it, and it is impossible to predict the questions of the future. Who decides the definition of “no further value”?

Trust has been eroded in the “neutrality” of recordkeepers following the destruction of documents such as the Windrush landing cards,¹ but the reality is that archives cannot keep everything, despite Jenkinson’s belief to the contrary.

It is vital that there is transparency at this stage of the process, with evidence of decisions taken. In the spirit of “who polices the police”, it is also important to ask, “where are the records of the record keepers”?

Cataloguing

It is perhaps in intellectual control that the archivist wields the most power and must be the most hyperaware. The way a collection is structured, its provenance determined and detailed, the way in which it is catalogued, and the words used to describe its contents will all determine the way in

² In 2010 the Home Office destroyed thousands of archival records detailing arrival dates of West Indians to the UK, despite warnings from immigration experts.

which future users will access it, and these decisions are frequently made by those with no direct connection to, or deep understanding of, the subject matter. Given the range of material many archives handle, this is perhaps no surprise.

In working towards culturally sensitive management of collections, it becomes imperative to consult with, and listen to, representatives of those who do have a connection with the subject matter. Not only does this reduce (although not eliminate) the risk of bias or unintentional ignorance, but it goes some way to shifting the power balance from the archivist to the archived.

When cataloguing archives related to Britain's colonial past, the issues are manifold. Outdated and offensive terminology proliferates, but the best way in which to tackle this remains debated. Archivists have a duty to preserve the integrity of the record but also to assist and support the users of that record. There is, of course, no question of altering original documents, but how should those documents be described in finding aids in a way that neither whitewashes the truth of their content nor offends or distresses those looking through finding aids? These decisions have access ramifications, as will be discussed below.

Multiple solutions to the descriptive practices question have been proposed, from asking relevant user groups to create tags for a collection to incorporating both the original wording and an alternate wording in a description, but there is no simple solution. Who should decide which words or phrases are offensive or are likely to be offensive in the future? What should be done with words that are not intrinsically offensive, such as "owner", but which are altered by their context, as in "slave owner". Is it enough to place a content warning at the beginning of collections to advise that material contains outdated wording, or is there a further obligation?

The extensive work of Carissa Chew² and of Alicia Chilcott³, among others, is evidence of the profession's desire to face these issues, but implementing solutions is time-consuming and would frequently have to be done retrospectively to collections which have been catalogued for decades.

Beyond the thorny issue of terminology in collections that deal explicitly with colonialism, there is the question of provenance. Should archivists actively dig into the provenance of record creators to highlight their connections to colonialism even when those connections aren't immediately obvious within the collection? If so, should that ideally be retrospectively applied to all collections held by an institution? Walch (1994, p. 2), with other members of the Working Group on Standards for Archival Description, defines archival description as "the process of capturing, collating, analysing, and organising any information that serves to identify, manage, locate, and interpret the holdings of archival institutions and explain the contexts and records systems from which those holdings were selected", but this presents numerous challenges, as witnessed by the pilot project undertaken to

2 More information about the work of Carissa Chew can be found at <https://carissachew.com/> and <https://culturalheritageterminology.co.uk/>

3 Alicia Chilcott's work on promoting inclusive practice within archives includes developing a series of protocols for describing racially offensive language.

uncover “slave-ownership” within St. Andrews University Special Collections (Buncombe & Prest, 2022).⁴

Many collections were, of course, catalogued prior to the invention of the internet, with its ability to pull up information in seconds, and most archives will simply have neither time nor resource to accomplish this retrospectively, but without doing so, the archive continues to tell half a story.

Access

It is generally acknowledged today that providing access is part of custodial responsibility, and perhaps particularly a responsibility to those represented within a collection – the voiceless part of the provenance. But the word “access”, while suggesting openness, is loaded. It reinforces where power lies and emphasises the fact that the organisation that holds a collection can grant or deny that access.

While the provision of access is increasingly recognized as a significant, even primary component of the custodial obligation, access remains a contested notion and practice within debates on decolonizing archives and colonial heritage. If there is a consensus that documented communities are entitled to facilitated access to the records containing their histories, that access is often implicated in and conditioned by power differentials that complicate, and may undermine, decolonial aspirations. (Agostinho, 2019, p. 151)

In addition, the word “access” has multiple meanings which all need to be considered, from physical access to the building that houses a collection to the ability to read and understand it.

To access archive material related to Britain’s colonial past, that material needs to be catalogued in such a way that it is discoverable. Here the issue of terminology is once again paramount – leave the original wording as the description and you risk people not finding it. Change the wording and you risk rendering the description obsolete over time.

Another access challenge to archivists is that of impact on diverse users. Some, but not all, of those interacting with an archive, or with the finding aid or catalogue, will have a personal connection to the subject matter. They may be using it for one reason but at the same time be feeling a profound personal impact. Users’ experiences with any given document are not universal, and the archivist needs to be aware of the potential for trauma or distress.

Interpretation and engagement

Once a collection is catalogued and made accessible, at least in the traditional sense, what can or should archivists do with it? Is it the archivist’s role to simply act as a passive guardian of the record

⁴ This project sought to cross-reference the St Andrews University Special Collections catalogues against the Legacies of British Slave-ownership database (<https://www.ucl.ac.uk/lbs/>) and met with various challenges in both the process and the practicality.

or, assuming Jenkinson's vision of neutrality is unachievable, is there a responsibility to actively disseminate the information within archive collections?

If, as would seem likely, neutrality is impossible due to inbuilt systemic processes and structures both historic and current, how can we be sure of the right, culturally sensitive way to interpret archival material and engage diverse audiences? We return to the question which opened this paper – who is writing history and for whom? As a majority white profession, do we have the right to tell this story? Do we have the right not to?

Looking ahead

The responsibility of acting as conduit to the raw material of history is currently a matter of great and passionate discussion within the archive profession. The issues are manifold and systemic – it is not as simple as flagging offensive words. It is a challenge to diversify the profession, (part of the strategic vision of the Archives and Records Association)⁵, to re-examine the nature of custodial responsibility, to embed inclusivity in our professional standards through updating the Archives Accreditation process⁶, and to engage openly and meaningfully with a range of audiences. There are divisions within the sector about how to achieve these ends, and polarised opinions about what is needed.

The Archives and Records Association, the leading professional body for the archive sector in the UK and Ireland, is a signatory to the Heritage Alliance's Anti-Racism statement, which acknowledges that "our nation's history and heritage is an invaluable tool in the fight against racism and discrimination". ARA has developed a Diversity and Inclusion Allies Group to advise the sector on best practices, but for long-term change these discussions will need to be embedded into the education system that shapes the archive profession. If archive and records management courses do not address the issues raised in this paper, how will the next generations of archivists be equipped to engage with them meaningfully?

As the conduits through which many access history, archivists have both the power and responsibility to tackle these questions but need to be educated, resourced, and equipped to do so.

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⁵ Further information about the strategic priorities of the ARA can be found at <https://www.archives.org.uk/news/ara-publishes-its-equity-diversity-and-inclusion-strategic-direction-report>

⁶ Further information about the new focus areas for Archives Accreditation can be seen at (<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/archives-sector/archive-service-accreditation/archive-service-accreditation-10-year-review/>),

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Historiographical afterlives of *Capitalism and Slavery* (1944) and the Williams theses

Stephen Mullen

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Trinidadian historian Eric Williams's *Capitalism and Slavery* (1944) has been described as “perhaps the most influential book written in the twentieth century on the history of slavery” (Morgan, 2008). The book evolved from a doctoral thesis at St Catherine's College, Oxford, in 1938. Multiple publishers in Great Britain initially rejected the manuscript, with Fredric Warburg claiming: “I would never publish such a book, for it would be contrary to the British tradition” (Matera, 2018, 269). The book eventually appeared with the University of North Carolina Press in 1944 and was first published in the UK by André Deutsch 20 years later. When published as Penguin Classic in 2022, *Capitalism and Slavery* became an instant bestseller. This article here outlines why the seminal book retains relevance in the 21st century.

Capitalism and Slavery marked the shift in historiographical understandings, and wider societal perceptions, of the significance of British colonies, and by extension, chattel slavery, to the economic development of Great Britain. Chattel slavery was the economic foundation of the English colonies in North America and the West Indies. English colonisation began c.1603, with chattel slavery practised from 1661. After the Union between Scotland and England in 1707, this became the British Empire. English/British ships trafficked 3.25 million African people into slavery societies in the Americas (historically described as the ‘slave trade’), the second-highest numbers amongst all European colonial powers (Slave Voyages, Estimates). Despite this, glorious narratives of the British Empire's supposed benevolence prevailed by the early 20th century. Williams famously critiqued these approaches by commenting: “British historians wrote almost as if Britain had introduced Negro slavery solely for the satisfaction of abolishing it” (Williams, 1964, 182). Such historiographical accounts effectively minimised Great Britain's economic dependency on the colonies at a time of rapid transformation, thus obscuring the fundamental importance of the Atlantic slavery system to British economic and societal development.

Williams advanced four main arguments in *Capitalism and Slavery* (1944), which radically transformed how the relationship between Great Britain and her colonies in the British Atlantic world were viewed. Firstly, Williams argued that “slavery was not born of racism; rather, racism was the consequence of slavery” (Williams, 1944, 7). Secondly, Williams argued that Africa trafficking and plantation slavery were fundamental to the origins of Britain's Industrial Revolution (Williams, 1944, 126-135). A mercantile trade monopoly governed imports and exports between Britain and her colonies. Enslaved people in slavery societies produced commodities – sugar, tobacco and coffee – that were exported to Great Britain as luxuries and foodstuffs. Cotton, another slave-grown product, was spun in mills as textile manufacturing became the leading sector of Britain's industrial transformation, which employed large swathes of the population in a wider British-Atlantic slavery economy. Williams traced the profits accumulated by African traffickers, West India merchants and absentee planters that were invested across many British regions (Williams, 1944, 85-97). Thus,

the “commercial capitalism, slavery and all its works” of the 18th century “helped to create the industrial capitalism of the nineteenth century” (Williams, 1944, 210). For Williams, the effects across Great Britain were dramatic:

By 1750, there was hardly a trading or manufacturing town in England which was not in some way connected with the triangular or direct colonial trade. The profits provided one of the main streams of accumulation of capital in England which financed the Industrial Revolution. (Williams, 1944, 52)

Thirdly, Williams argued that Britain’s Atlantic slavery economy went into terminal decline, in terms of profitability and the wider influence of those involved, after the American Revolution in 1776 as the “center of gravity in the British Empire shifted from the Caribbean sea to the India Ocean” (Williams, 1944, 123). Williams thus advanced, following in the footsteps of mentor Lowell Ragatz, what has become known as “decline thesis”.

Fourthly, Williams argued that the Africa trafficking and plantation slavery in the British West Indies were abolished in 1807 and 1834 respectively for declining economic conditions rather than humanitarian factors. Overall, for Williams, mercantilism and its foundation, chattel slavery, underpinned the development of British industrial capitalism. As British manufacturing became more profitable, with the new industrial class focusing on new markets such as India and Brazil, the unprofitable British West Indies were no longer required. Abolitions in 1807 and 1834 respectively were an economic necessity, rather than an exemplar of the British Empire’s humanitarian benevolence (Williams, 1944, 178-197).

Beginning in the 1960s, historians adopted a sceptical view of Williams’s main argument that Africa trafficking and plantation slavery were central to the British Industrial Revolution. For example, some noted African slave trade voyages came with a great deal of risk and profits were smaller than he estimated, and so could not have financed wider industrialisation. Of course, Williams actually made a broader argument that, in addition to personal profits, British development was influenced by transatlantic trade with slavery societies (especially the Caribbean). However, a seminal paper by Eltis and Engerman (2000) argued that the sugar trade’s influence upon British economic development was limited and therefore the contribution of slavery was negligible. However, this paper has been critiqued for its “straw man” demolition of an argument that Williams did not make: that slavery “caused the Industrial Revolution” (Hall et al., 2014, 29). Nevertheless, commenting in right-wing think tank *History Reclaimed* in December 2023, Rashid J. Griffith (2023) invoked the Eltis/Engerman article, apparently unaware of the dramatic historiographical shift now firmly behind the main Williams thesis.

There is increasing consensus amongst the leading economic historians of Great Britain that slavery and its commerce was a major influence upon British economic development. The Legacies of British Slaveownership projects (LBS) at University College London, and Nicholas Draper in particular, examined British residents who claimed compensation from the British government when plantation slavery was abolished in 1834, producing a database of absentee enslavers in Great Britain. Successive LBS projects (2009-2012; 2013-15) have provided the most significant interventions in the historiographical debates around the Williams theses. Firstly, *Capitalism and*

Slavery was interpreted in a new way, noting that Williams advanced a distinct thesis about the private profits derived from slavery (Hall et al., 2014). Williams was accused of invoking examples of grandiose absentees devoid of analytical context, thus inviting accusations that he over-emphasised the significance of slavery-derived investments relative to wider processes (Williams, 1944, 85-97). The LBS dataset facilitated assessments of representativeness. Secondly, the LBS project advanced a modified Williams thesis: arguing that whilst Williams envisioned Atlantic slavery as central to Britain's 18th-century economic development, these processes continued into the 19th century, which was an important conclusion: Caribbean slavery was profitable across almost the entirety of the British Industrial Revolution era, c.1760-1830 (Draper, 2014, 11). Overall, the LBS team argued that Britain's Atlantic slavery economy was a "significant contributor" to British industry (particularly cotton and railways), and especially commerce, into the 1850s (Hall et al., 2014, 11).

Works by leading economic historians continue to underline the importance of Atlantic commerce and slavery to British development. Joseph Inikori (2002) underlined that wider Atlantic systems had significant multiplier effects on English industrialisation, shipping, and the commercial and financial infrastructure. Rönnbäck (2018) estimated that, rather than being marginal, slavery-associated economic activities represented the equivalent of 11 per cent of Great Britain's eighteenth-century GDP. Zahedieh's (2021) study of the copper industry in England endorsed William's vision of "commercial capitalism", showing how the Atlantic slavery economy underpinned growth in industries apparently unconnected to Africa trafficking and slavery. Berg and Hudson (2021) claimed that Atlantic commerce was a "major causal factor" in the British Industrial Revolution. The authors recently refined this argument, noting that "slavery certainly was formative in the timing and nature of Britain's industrial revolution" (Berg and Hudson, 2023, 12).

The Williams thesis on slavery and industrialisation is now orthodoxy in Scottish historiography. Ignored by almost all historians of Scotland writing in the late 20th century, it is now accepted that Atlantic slavery played a more disproportionate role in Scotland's economic development compared to England, Ireland or Wales (Devine 2015). Hamilton (2005) represented the first explicit endorsement of *Capitalism and Slavery* in a Scottish context. Subsequent works have outlined that Caribbean slavery was central to Scotland's economic development after 1760. Anthony Cooke (2012) noted the significance of West Indian merchant capital. Mullen (2022) mapped the repatriation of wealth by Scots in the West Indies, estimating returns of slavery-derived fortunes worth up to £894 million in modern values between 1784 and 1858. Investigations – such as "Slavery, abolition and the University of Glasgow" (Mullen & Newman, 2018), as well as *Historic Environment Scotland's Properties in care and the British Empire* (Mullen, Mackillop, Driscoll, 2024) – have confirmed the significance of Atlantic slavery and its commerce to Scottish institutions and landscapes. Scotland is now moving from a position of historiographical orthodoxy around the main Williams thesis to institutional truth-seeking and national interpretation related to the legacies of Empire and slavery.

Capitalism and Slavery remains fundamental to major debates around the history and legacies of Atlantic slavery in 21st century Britain. Williams's arguments are now more in favour amongst leading economic historians of Britain's Industrial Revolutions than at any other point since 1944. Once rejected by British publishers, written off by historians of England and ignored by historians of Scotland, it remains the starting point for scholars in the fields of Atlantic world and Caribbean

history, and increasingly for those studying Scottish and English economic change. Eric Williams, and the Williams theses, remain a topic of everyday discussion 80 years after its first publication.

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Teaching and learning with and through *Capitalism and Slavery*

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Capitalism and Slavery is one of a small group of historical texts still widely taught generations after their publication (another is the text by Williams’s fellow Trinidadian, C.L.R. James’s *The Black Jacobins*). It is taught at university level, including in my own undergraduate and postgraduate courses. In schools, at least in the UK, the educational system with which I’m most familiar, students are less likely to engage directly with Williams’s prose, but they are exposed to his ideas through two debates that remain central to the way in which the subject is taught: the question of the extent to which the Atlantic slave system contributed to the development of British capitalism and the industrial revolution, and the discussion of the relationship between economic self-interest and humanitarianism in leading to the eventual abolition of the slave trade and slavery. Indeed, the latter debate forms a core part of the Scottish Qualifications Authority course on The Atlantic Slave Trade 1770-1707, taught to 15- and 16-year-olds studying history across Scotland. A typical exam question asks pupils, “How important were economic circumstances to the eventual success of the abolition campaign?” They are expected, in response, to weigh the economic alongside a range of other factors’ contributions to abolition (of the slave trade) in 1807. These debates – the “Williams debate(s)” – also frequently frame the way Williams is used in university curricula.

These two Williams debates are indeed critically important and continue to generate new historical research. This is perhaps particularly true of the first Williams debate on the contribution of slavery to the industrial revolution. Maxine Berg and Pat Hudson’s recent synthetic book on *Slavery, Capitalism and the Industrial Revolution* is testament to that, as is the recent book of my fellow panellist Stephen Mullen (*The Glasgow sugar aristocracy*), and the publications on the copper industry of my former colleague Nuala Zahedieh.¹ While in some circles of economic history, scholars still claim that the contribution of colonialism was insignificant — that industrialisation would have happened first in Britain anyway — this argument no longer attracts much support beyond very specific quarters of economic historians and the publications of certain conservative think tanks. The counterfactual claim that industrialisation *could and would have happened* even without slavery is, after all, not very relevant in light of the reality that it *did* in fact happen with slavery. In contexts of teaching and learning, the myriad connections between specific British locations, families, and institutions and the Caribbean are particularly valuable, providing tangible connections that students at school and university level can make between places familiar to them and the world of Caribbean slavery. In the Teaching Slavery in Scotland project with which I’ve been involved since 2022, some of the most powerful material produced by schoolteacher participants has explored the connections of Scottish

1 Berg, M. (2023). *Slavery, capitalism and the Industrial Revolution* Polity; Mullen, S. (2022). *The Glasgow sugar aristocracy: Scotland and Caribbean slavery, 1775-1838* University of London Press; Zahedieh, N. (2021). Eric Williams and William Forbes: Copper, colonial markets, and commercial capitalism, *The Economic History Review* 74(3),784–808, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ehr.13050>.

industries such as linen, fishing, sugar refining, and banking to Caribbean slavery.² Similarly, the community performance project Living Histories of Sugar was particularly powerful in the way it connected the history of sugar in the Caribbean to the development of the Scottish sweet tooth.³ That is to say, this is a narrative that makes intuitive as well as intellectual sense to learners because of the tangible connections between the present and the past.

The second Williams debate has, in some ways, moved on, but in ways that again provide renewed appreciation for Williams's work. For a long time, historians' discussions of the causes of British abolition were largely metropolitan-focused and framed within the British Atlantic system. In part they took the lead from Williams's book but also from the much more dominant school of thought to which he was responding, the view that British abolition was achieved primarily as a result of the development of humanitarian principles in Britain, leading to political pressure. In a complicated series of debates that spun through the 1970s and 80s, historians addressed myriad reasons for abolition and emancipation, including Williams's argument that profits from the Caribbean colonies were declining, but also importantly attending to the rise of new working-class publics, the ideological attraction of a binary understanding of slavery, and antislavery as displacement from consideration of harsh forms of exploitation under regimes of wage labour, both in Britain and elsewhere.⁴

More recently greater attention has been paid to some other areas that were anticipated by Williams. The first is attention to the role of enslaved people in bringing about the end of slavery through armed rebellion, which Williams addresses in the penultimate chapter of *Capitalism and Slavery*, in "The slaves and slavery". As he sharply pointed out, "The slaves ... were not prepared to wait for freedom to come to them as a dispensation from above" (Williams, 1967, p. 204). Newer historiography emphasizes that enslaved people's military action — in Haiti, Barbados, Demerara and Jamaica — eventually convinced metropolitan governments that the costs of maintaining slavery were too high, both in terms of literal costs of maintaining a strong military presence in the Caribbean to defend slavery in the colonies and in terms of reputation and prestige (Blackburn, 1988; Fergus, 2013; Matthews, 2006).⁵ This is an important historiographical development, though not a straightforward one; it is easy to oversimplify especially in contexts of teaching and learning.

2 Resources produced by teachers involved in the Teaching Slavery in Scotland project can be seen on the Scottish Association of Teachers of History website, <http://www.sath.org.uk/teaching-slavery-in-scotland-project/> (last accessed 4 March 2024).

3 Living Histories of Sugar, <https://www.sugarhistories.co.uk/> (last accessed 4 March 2024). The project was led by Marisa Wilson and brought together performers from Scotland and the Caribbean. I was involved as historical advisor.

4 Important contributions to this literature include Davis, D. B. (1975). *The problem of slavery in the age of revolution, 1770-1823*. Cornell University Press; Drescher, S. (1986). *Capitalism and antislavery: British mobilization in comparative perspective*. Macmillan; Eltis, D. (1987). *Economic growth and the ending of the Atlantic slave trade*. Oxford University Press; Carrington, S. H. H. (2002). *The sugar industry and the abolition of the slave trade, 1775-1810*. University Press of Florida.

5 For older work that also addressed the theme see Turner, M. (1982). *Slaves and missionaries: The disintegration of Jamaican slave society, 1787-1834*. University of Illinois Press; Hart, R. (1985). *Slaves who abolished slavery*. Institute of Social and Economic Research.

Enslaved people fought back against slavery throughout the centuries of its existence, but their earlier struggles did not lead to the end of slavery or the slave trade. The 1760 war in Jamaica led by Tacky and others went on for months and was brutally suppressed. It led to harsher slave codes and to reflections by people like Edward Long that more white plantation residents were needed in the colonies, but not the end of slavery. Revolutionary antislavery in the Caribbean interacted with a changed political conjuncture in Britain to have long-lasting results. British governments only judged slave rebellion to be too costly because abolitionist campaigners, using the new tools of mass communication available to them, had brought into being a public in Britain that was attentive to what was happening in the colonies. Elizabeth Heyrick's stirring pamphlet *Immediate, not Gradual Abolition*, published in 1824 in the aftermath of the Demerara rebellion and the first to call for immediate emancipation in the period of the revived anti-slavery campaign of the 1820s, is an example (which I use in my own teaching) of the interaction between enslaved people's actions in the Caribbean and those of radical abolitionists in Britain. This is one of many examples of why the isolation of individual factors to explain historical change, as demanded by some forms of history assessment at the school level, can inhibit the development of historical understanding.

Alongside this increasing attention to enslaved people's antislavery mobilisation, Williams also anticipated much greater attention to British ongoing investments in societies dominated by slavery in the era after British abolition, particularly Cuba, Brazil and the United States. Recent and forthcoming work by Chris Evans and Joseph Mulhern develops at greater length the points made by Williams in chapter 10 of *Capitalism and Slavery* where he emphasizes the failure of abolitionists to achieve restrictions on British investment in slavery or ownership of enslaved people beyond British imperial territory and the major investments of Britons in these regions (Mulhern, 2024; Evans, 2013). This is an area that is currently much less attended to in the teaching of the history of slavery in the UK.

Finally, I want to draw attention to another Williams debate that gets less attention in the current moment than the other two. Williams argues that "Slavery was not born of racism; rather, racism was the consequence of slavery" (William, 1967, p. 7). In de-emphasizing racism, Williams's claim is less in tune with contemporary political directions than are some of his other arguments. More importantly — and perhaps relatedly — many aspects of recent (and some less recent) scholarship suggest that Williams's claim here was too bold. To name a few: David Eltis's (2000) emphasis on the 'enslavability' of Africans to Europeans and the non-enslavability of Europeans; Jennifer Morgan's (2021) tracking of racism in some of the earliest encounters between Europeans and Africans; Cedric Robinson's (1983) suggestion that the roots of racism can be found in European culture from medieval times; Michael Guasco's (2014) recognition that British slavery drew heavily on its encounters with Iberian slavery, which were themselves deeply rooted in the racializing process of the *Reconquista*; and Hannah Barker's (2019) emphasis that the slave trade in the Mediterranean, which was another precursor of Atlantic slavery, was built on othering of enslaved people from across the Black Sea. All these flows of scholarship emphasise that racism was there from the beginning and contributed to the emergence of the enslavement of Africans as the dominant labour form in Britain's American colonies.

Despite this, Williams's emphasis on the importance of white indentured and convict labour as a predecessor and parallel to slavery — which forms an important part of the evidence he provides

for his claim about the priority of slavery rather than racism — is well taken. It is important to note here that neither Williams nor current historians argue that indenture was equivalent to enslavement. Rather, as Simon Newman among others have emphasized, aspects of the treatment of indentured workers cleared the way for British comfort with enslavement and the violence and brutality it entailed (Newman, 2013). Historical thinking requires understanding of the interaction of different aspects of the past rather than the isolation of one as preminent.

As I hope this summary has shown, *Capitalism and Slavery* is a rich text that goes beyond a singular Williams thesis, providing ongoing stimulation for historical debate on multiple levels. The opportunities to use the text in teaching and learning today remain substantial. I look forward to further discussion at the conference in June.

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Street names and built landscape: Scottish colonial imprint on Barbados

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There are times when a visitor to Barbados takes a cool afternoon drive through the north-eastern region of Barbados, gazing at the spectacularly eroded landscape, ravines, terraces and streams. What they observe is the enduring Scottish colonial imprint. As they follow the road from Bathsheba through Newcastle and Consett Bay, they are likely to see the descendants of the Scottish and Irish indentured labourers known as Redlegs. As the coach moves out of the Scotland District into the St George Valley and Christ Church ridge, they will see place names such as Arthur Seat and Bannatyne. The tour enters Bridgetown where the visitor takes a tour of Bethel Methodist church and the Barbados Museum, where Scottish names are emblazoned on the red bricks of these buildings. As the tour guide mentions surnames such as Boyce and Cleland, that curious visitor would have been immersed in the Scottish colonial imprint.

This paper has two objectives. First, it discusses the origins, nature and persistence of this imprint, especially considering Barbados's move to independence in 1966 and republicanism in 2021. Second, against the background of decolonization and a strident call for reparations, the paper explores how that imprint could be embraced as a strong “teaching point” on the impact of British colonialism for heritage tourism. My central thesis is that the existing colonial imprint should be perceived not merely as a negative throw back of British colonialism but as a “country museum of colonialism,” which can be a critical plank of heritage tourism. Jamaica has a strong imperial heritage consisting of Great Houses, and the authorities have determined that such colonial relics must not be torn down or left to rot but commercially exploited in what is termed “dark tourism” (Simpson, 2024). But this tourism is not merely about Great Houses, windmills and burial grounds; it is about the captivating, authentic stories drawn from historical research that transport the visitor back in time to bring understanding to the present landscape.

The role of the Scottish settlers and indentured servants in the British Caribbean has been well documented in Eric Williams's *Capitalism and Slavery* (2005/1944). The first appointed proprietor of Barbados was Sir James Hay, the first Earl of Carlisle, who, in July 1627, obtained a grant of the Caribbean islands including Barbados. He organised the production, labour and capital and paid the Crown 10% of the earnings of the colonies. In Barbados, a prominent bay is named after him, and Carlisle Bay became the island's principal port from 1627 to 1961. It is now a haven for pleasure craft and water sports. Further into the city itself, Carlisle House stands as a sentinel, guarding the entrance of the Careenage. Many of the Scottish settlers who came established small farms, hired indentured servants and used African enslaved labour to cultivate these plots that would later produce sugar, molasses and rum. For example, David Dobson has shown that in 1679, James Alexander, militiaman in St Philip, owned 100 acres, employing two servants and enslaved Africans. Andrew Boyce, using a 12 acre-plot, employed three slaves in St Lucy in 1678. The surname Boyce is still a popular name in the parish today. Col William Cleland, also of Scotland, served as an

assemblyman in 1699, and while this is not a popular surname, there is a plantation in the parish of St Peter/St Andrew which carries the name (Dobson, 1989).

Dobson's research reveals the origin and nature of this system of indentured servitude. William Dundas, described as a "time-expired indentured servant" emigrated from Barbados to Virginia August 1679. So too George Gordon, also "time expired", emigrated to Carolina in August 1679 (Dobson, 1989). Yet many stayed in the country and are now known as the Redlegs, or poor whites, because of their sun-burned legs. Undoubtedly, these Scottish migrants (settlers and servants) were the ones to append place names such as Arthur Seat, Bannatyne, Moncrieffe, Castle Grant, Inch Marlow and Rouen (Marshall, 2016).

The merchant ships arriving from Glasgow were loaded with red bricks or ballast bricks, designed to stabilise vessels on the outward voyage to the Caribbean. There was no need to return to Europe with these bricks, as ships arrived in Europe laden with colonial produce. Thus, most of Bridgetown's stone buildings were constructed with red bricks, some carrying Scottish manufacturing names.

The Scottish imprint on the landscape is even more pronounced in the hilly north-eastern section of the island, first called Scotland and now called the Scotland District. This area, characterised by hills as high as 1000 feet, deep ravines and gullies, accounts for one-seventh of Barbados. The long history of erosion and land slippage have created some pulsating stories. For instance, in 1901, a small plantation mill at Breedy's plantation disappeared during the flood and landside of that year only to reappear during the widespread flooding in 1938, then disappear again (Marshall, 2016).

In 1966, as Barbados moved slowly to independence and achieved it, there was no significant rupturing of the colonial imprint. The national flag proudly displayed a British emblem, the trident (albeit broken), and it is not by accident that the day chosen for this momentous break with colonialism was November 30, St Andrew's Day. Even as Barbados was well entrenched as an independent country and had the chance to rename certain roads, it did not. The case in point is the recent naming of Fusilier Road at Gun Hill, St George, where a Scottish regiment had taken up residence. The sign reads: "Fusilier Road. This road was built by the Royal Scots Fusiliers, the twenty-first regiment, during their stay at Gun Hill from September 1862 until February 1863".

Over the last two decades, there have been stringent calls in the former colonies to remove certain colonial names and statues. In Barbados, Trafalgar Square was renamed "Heroes Square" in 1999, and two decades later, the statue of Lord Nelson, which had adorned the site for over 200 years, was removed. A more suitable monument depicting the chains of enslavement, dedicated to the family and the outstanding Barbadians produced from those families, has now taken the place of Lord Nelson. While the Nelson statue was offensive to the sensibilities of the Barbadian people who had been enslaved, British place names in Bridgetown and the rural districts still abound. My argument, therefore, is it would be folly to erase the colonial imprint by renaming all of them. With an economy driven by tourism, the colonial imprint can be used creatively for heritage tourism to demonstrate to locals and visitors alike the nature and impact of the colonial experience or what has been described as "dark tourism".

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